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2.	Arziev Ismoil Alievich TECHNIQUE AND FEATURES OF SURGICAL CORRECTION OF DAMAGE TO THE MAIN BILE DUCTS THAT OCCURRED INTRAOPERATIVELY.....	17
3.	Anarboev Sanjar Alisherovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF RECURRENT FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....	26
4.	Askarova Nafisa Rinatovna VULVARICOSITY: FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH VARICOSE VEINS AND PREGNANT WOMEN.....	33
5.	Akhmedov Rakhmatillo Furkatovich SURGICAL TACTICS FOR IATROGENIC INJURIES TO THE BILE DUCTS.....	38
6.	Achilov Mirzakarim Temirovich SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PANCREATIC HEAD TUMORS.....	44
7.	Allazov Iskandar Salakh ogli CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS: RETROSPECTIVE ASPECTS AND MODERN VIEWS.....	49
8.	Allazov Salakh Allazovich LAPAROSCOPIC AND RETROPERITONEOSCOPIC OPERATIONS IN UROLOGY...	57
9.	Bobokulov Nurullo Asadovich, Ablyatifov Aziz Baxriyarovich OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT IN UROLOGY: THE ROLE OF SIMULTANEOUS LAPAROSCOPIC OPERATIONS.....	66
10.	Bakhriddinov Bekzod Rustamovich, Aliev Mansur Abduholikovich MR SPECTROSCOPY OF BRAIN TUMORS AND CORRELATION OF METABOLIC CHANGES WITH HISTOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS.....	72
11.	Davronov Alisher Uktamovich, Kurbaniyazov Bobojon Zafarjonovich LAPAROSCOPIC REPAIR OF PERFORATED ULCERS: ADVANTAGES AND CLINICAL OUTCOMES.....	79
12.	Daminov Feruz Asatullaevich, Bobokulov Azamat Uktamovich FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BLEEDING IN GASTRODUODENAL ULCERS. (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	88
13.	Davronov Oybek Otabek ugli MODERN VIEWS ON THE PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CHANGES IN THE FORNICAL APPARATUS AND ADJACENT STRUCTURES DURING URINARY STONE DISEASE.....	95
14.	Egamberdiev Abdukakhkhor Abdukodirovich FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF HERNIA OF THE ESOPHAGEAL HOLE OF THE DIAPHRAGM.....	101
15.	Esirgapov Sardor Nursalimovich, Abduraxmanov Diyor Shukrullaevich RESULTS OF HERNIOPLASTY OF VENTRAL HERNIAS WITH ABDOMINOPTOSIS.....	106
16.	Gafarov Rushen Refatovich CLASSIFICATION OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS OF HOLMIUM LASER ENUCLEATION OF THE PROSTATE: ROLE OF A UNIFIED APPROACH.....	112
17.	Giyasova Nigora Kobilovna MODERN APPROACHES TO DETECTING ARTHROSIS AT EARLY STAGES AND POSSIBILITIES OF PATHOGENETIC TREATMENT OF THIS DISEASE.....	118

18.	Ishmuradov Bakhron Tursunovich EFFICACY OF ENDOSCOPIC BALLOON DILATION IN TREATMENT OF ACQUIRED URETERAL STRICTURES.....	127
19.	Islomov Nuriddin Komil ugli, Mustafakulov Ishnazar Boynazarovich, Julbekov Komil Islomovich MANAGEMENT FOR SIGMOID VOLVULUS.....	131
20.	Ismati Amir Olimovich, Mamarajabov Sobirjon Ergashevich, Anosov Viktor Davidovich A NOVEL PROGNOSTIC SYSTEM FOR 30-DAY MORTALITY IN PATIENTS WITH ULCER UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING.....	141
21.	Jalilov Khusan Mukhidinovich, Mansurov Jaloliddin Shamsiddinovich PREOPERATIVE INCIDENCE OF DEEP VEIN THROMBOSIS AFTER HIP FRACTURES IN KOREANS.....	151
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24.	Kurbaniyazov Zafar Babajanovich, Mukhiddinov Bobur Khuroz Ugli, Askarov Pulat Azadovich EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY.....	168
25.	Khaidarov Numon Bozor ugli, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....	175
26.	Khalimova Zamira Yusufovna, Narimova Gulchehra Jumaniyazovna, Kurbanova Sitora Shukhratovna, Ablakulova Munisa Xamrakulovna INTERACTION BETWEEN MELATONIN AND METABOLIC PARAMETERS IN OBESE WOMEN: A CLINICAL ANALYSIS.....	181
27.	Khurazov Ganisher Mususrmonovich MODERN APPROACHES TO TREATING PROSTACH ADENOMA: EFFICIENCY, SAFETY, AND IMPACT ON PATIENTS' LIFE QUALITY.....	190
28.	Khursanov Yokubjon Erkin ugli, Sattorov Abbos Xalilovich EFFICIENCY OF USING MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS.....	196
29.	Khamrakulov Shokhrukh Farukhovich, Mamarajabov Sobirzhon Irgashevich, Rasulov Khamidulla Abdullaevich LAPAROSCOPIC TREATMENT OF STRICTURED HERNIAS OF THE ANTERIOR ABDOMINAL WALL.....	201
30.	Khodjimatom Gulomidin Minkhodzhievich, Yigitov Ayubkhon Azizbekovich, Yahyoev Sardorbek Mamasobir ugli IMPROVING THE OUTCOMES OF TREATMENT OF COMBINED SURGICAL DISEASES OF ABDOMINAL ORGANS USING SIMULTANEOUS LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERIES.....	207
31.	Khaidarov Numon Bozor ugli, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....	217

32.	Khamdamov Olim Dilmurodovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich OPTIMIZATION OF TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....	223
33.	Khashimov Rustam Uktamjanovich, Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INGUINAL HERNIAS.....	229
34.	Mamanov Muhammad Chorievich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TACTICS IN COMPLICATED AND COMPLEX FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....	235
35.	Mamatov Karim Saidullaevich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CHOLANGITIS.....	243
36.	Mardonov Bobosher Amirovich. SURGICAL TACTICS FOR POSTCHOLECYSTECTOMY SYNDROME: FEATURES AND CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTATION.....	249
37.	Mukhiddinov Temur Djakhangirovich, Askarov Pulat Azadovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF VENTRAL HERNIAS WITH CONCOMITANT PATHOLOGY OF ABDOMINAL ORGANS.....	256
38.	Mansurov Jalolidin Shamsidinovich COMPARISON OF ULTRASOUND-GUIDED HYDROSTATIC REDUCTION OF INTUSSUSCEPTION RESULTS BETWEEN PEDIATRIC AND NON-PEDIATRIC RADIOLOGISTS AND RESIDENTS.....	262
39.	Musoyev Sodikjon Toirovich MODERN ALGORITHMS FOR THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS: FROM CONSERVATIVE THERAPY TO SURGERY.....	273
40.	Negmatov Ismatillo Savridinovich CT DIAGNOSTICS, CLASSIFICATIONS, AND DEVELOPMENT OF A REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR ACUTE DIVERTICULITIS OF THE COLON.....	279
41.	Normamatov Bakhridin Pirmamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich OPTIMIZATION OF COMPREHENSIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ACUTE PURULENT CHOLANGITIS USING HYBRID MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES.....	293
42.	Nurillayev Khasan Zhamshidovich ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS IN THE ELDERLY: FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....	300
43.	Obidov Shokhrukh Khabibovich, Mamarajabov Sobirjon Ergashevich MODERN APPROACHES TO SURGICAL TREATMENT OF INGUINAL HERNIAS IN OBESE PATIENTS.....	306
44.	Rabbimova Maftuna Ulugbekovna. ENDOSCOPIC ULTRASOUND ELASTOGRAPHY: CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENTAL DIRECTIONS.....	313
45.	Rakhmatov Istodjon Samedjonovich THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF X-RAY EXAMINATIONS IN MEDICINE.....	337
46.	Ruziboyev Sanjar Abdusalomovich, Allaberdiyev Nemat Abdushukurovich, Shavazi Ramiz Nuralievich REMOTE RESULTS OF THE IMPROVED LIXTENSHTEIN MODIFICATION.....	343
47.	Ruziboev Sanjar Abdusalomovich, Mardonov Vohid Narzullayevich, Shavazi Ramiz Nuralievich EXPERIMENT OF APPLYING ANTI-ADHESIVE PREPARATIONS IN THE EXPERIMENT.....	352

48.	Rizayev Jasur Alimjanovich, Abdullayev Sayfulla Abdullayevich THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PURULENT-NECROTIC INFLAMMATION OF SOFT TISSUES.....	360
49.	Rizayev Ezoz Alimdjanovich, Kurbaniyazov Zafarjon Babajanovich PREDICTION OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS OUTCOMES BASED ON LAPAROSCOPY DATA AND THE BALTHAZAR SCALE.....	365
50.	Ravshanov Mukhammadali Ikhtiyorovich, Askarov Pulat Azadovich MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE OF BENIGN ORIGIN.....	373
51.	Rashidova Xurshida Abduvoxiidovna POSSIBILITIES OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY AND INSTRUMENTAL STUDIES IN NON – ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....	379
52.	Salimov Eshdavlat Eshmakhmatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH THYROID NODULES.....	386
53.	Sayinaev Farrukh Karamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich ASPECTS OF LAPAROSCOPIC HERNIOPLASTY FOR VENTRAL HERNIAS.....	392
54.	Salokhiddinov Jurabek Saidakhmatovich TOPICAL ISSUES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF TOXIC FORMS OF GOITER...397	397
55.	Suvonov Shokhrux Shukhrat ugli CURRENT METHODS OF TREATMENT OF LARGE AND GIANT VENTRAL HERNIAS USING TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY.....	403
56.	Shirov Bobur Furkatovich, Mardieva Gulshod Mamatmuradova EVALUATION OF THE DIAGNOSTIC EFFECTIVENESS OF THE BONE COVERAGE COEFFICIENT AND SIDE RATIO COEFFICIENT COMPARED TO THE GRAF METHOD.....	409
57.	Shomurodov Khabibullo Abdumalik ugli, Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich APPLICATION OF LAPAROSCOPY IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE CHOLECYSTITIS.....	419
58.	Turakulov Vali Norkulovich. MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE (COPD).....	424
59.	Tagaev Abror Ilkhomovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PURULENT PLEURISIS.....	430
60.	Toirov Abdukhomit Suvonovich, Musoev Sodiqjon Toirovich THE ROLE OF ENDOVENOUS LASER COAGULATION IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF VARICOSE VEINS OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....	437
61.	Turdumatov Jamshed Anvarovich, Sobirova Nilufar RADIOLOGICAL SEMIOTICS OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE IN TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS.....	442
62.	Tukhtayev Firdavs Mukhidinovich, Ergashev Arslonbek Shukhratjon ugli LAPAROSCOPIC TREATMENT OF CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS: EFFICACY AND RESULTS.....	451
63.	Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich, THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF VIDEOLAPAROSCOPY IN CLOSED ABDOMINAL INJURIES.....	457
64.	Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich IMPROVEMENTS IN DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC CAPABILITIES OF VIDEOLAPAROSCOPY WITH CLOSED ABDOMINAL LESIONS.....	463

65. **Usarov Sherali Nasretidinovich**
ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INGUINAL HERNIAS.....474
66. **Yanova Elvira Umarjonovna, Urokov Farrukh Ibodullaevich**
TYPES OF ANGIODYSPLASIA IN KIMMERLE ANOMALY BY MAGNETIC RESONANCE ANGIOGRAPHY.....479
67. **Yuldashev Parda Arzikulovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich, Davlatov Salim Sulaymonovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL APPROACHES IN THE TREATMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIAS.....491
68. **Alisher Zayniyev Faridunovich**
A NEW PLASMAPHERESIS METHOD FOR PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION IN PATIENTS WITH THYROTOXICOSIS.....499
69. **Ablyazov Otabek Vakhobovich, Yakubov Golib Akbarovich, Ablyazov Abduvakhob Abdumadzhidovich, Madumarova Zarnigor Shukhratovna, Turgunov Shomakhmud Shorakhimovich**
IMAGING METHODS FOR CERVICAL SPINAL CANAL STENOSIS.....508
70. **Kurbaniyazov Bakhodir Zafarzhonovich, Ashurov Akmal Khusanovich**
TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF TRANSABDOMINAL LAPAROSCOPIC HERNIALLOPLASTY FOR INGUINAL HERNIAS.....512
71. **Kilichev Rashid Nematovich, Mamarajabov Sobirjon Ergashevich, Babakalanov Shuhrat Ibragimovich, Oltiyev Elyor Doniyorovich.**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HAL-RAR AND LHP SURGICAL APPROACHES IN THE TREATMENT OF HEMORRHOIDS.....520
72. **Ahmedov Gayrat Keldibayevich, Gulamov Olimjon Mirzakhitovich, Azizov Temur Alisher ugli, Toshkenboyev Firdavs Ramatillo Zoda, Khudaynazarov Utkir Rabbimovich.**
ANASTOMOSIS IN ESOPHAGULAR CANCER OPERATIONS.....526
73. **Teshayev Shuxrat Jumayevich, Jarilkasinova Gauzar Januzakovna.**
SOCIAL AND CLINICAL-BIOCHEMICAL FACTORS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF GASTRITIS AND ULCER DISEASE: STUDYING SMOKING AND PROFESSIONAL DEPENDENCE.....531
74. **Khaibullina Zarina Ruslanovna, Babajanov Azam Khasanovich, Djuraeva Nigora Mukhsumovna, Abdukhalimova Khanum Valentinovna**
VON WILLEBRAND FACTOR DYNAMICS AFTER RELATED LIVER TRANSPLANTATION.....538
75. **Khaydarova Nargiza Akhtamzhon kizi**
ANALYSIS OF MORPHOFUNCTIONAL AND MORPHOMETRIC FEATURES OF THE THYROID GLAND IN 5-MONTH-OLD MONGREL RATS IN THE OBSERVATION GROUP.....549
76. **Mardiyeva Gulshod Mamatmuradovna, Abdullaeva Mukhiba Nigmatovna, Matyakupov Azim Rustemovich, Nurmamatova Ozoda Abdurasul kizi.**
ROENTGEN-PROTEINOLOGICAL RELATIONSHIPS IN THE DYNAMICS OF PNEUMONIA IN NEWBORNS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DEGREE OF THEIR MATURITY.....556
77. **Karabyev Djamshidkhan Shavkatovich, Shakhanov Shavkat Safarovich, Shakirov Bobur**
PREVENTION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTHRITIS IN PATIENTS WITH BURNS USING LOW VIBRATION LASER BEAMS.....564
78. **Исмаилов Зоҳиджан, Мирджурев Элбек**
ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ПЕРИФЕРИЧЕСКОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ, ИХ ДИАГНОСТИКА, ВЫБОР ПРАВИЛЬНОЙ ТАКТИКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ И ШИРОКОЕ ВНЕДРЕНИЕ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИОННОЙ РАБОТЫ ПОСЛЕ ПЕРЕНЕСЕННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ...570
79. **Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek**
EXAMINATION OF CHILDREN WITH NEUROPATHY, TIMELY DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND REHABILITATION MEASURES AFTER ILLNESSES.....578

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ENDOSCOPIC CHARACTERISTICS OF GASTRODUODENAL COMPLICATIONS IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS

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ANNOTATION

The use of 7 parameters as the main prognostic criteria for assessing the condition of a victim with extensive thermal trauma complicated by the development of burn disease is justified. A comprehensive analysis of these criteria makes it possible to create a scale for predicting the development of acute gastroduodenal complications, the high reliability of which will allow predicting the development of these complications and taking timely preventive measures.

Keywords: burn injury, burn disease, gastroduodenal complications, injury severity index.

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ОҒИР КУЙГАНЛАРДА ЎТКИР ГАСТРОДУОДЕНАЛ АСОРАТЛАРИНИНГ ЭНДОСКОПИК ТАВСИФИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Куйиш касаллиги ривожланган беморлар ҳолатини баҳолашнинг асосий прогностик мезонлари сифатида 7 параметрдан фойдаланиш асосланган. Ушбу мезонларни ҳар томонлама таҳлил қилиш ўткир гастродуоденал асоратларни ривожланишини башорат қилиш миқёсини

яратишга имкон беради, уларнинг юқори ишончилиги ушбу асоратларнинг ривожланишини башорат қилиш ва ўз вақтида профилактика чораларини кўриш имконини беради

Калит сўзлар: куйиш жароҳати, куйиш касаллиги, гастродуоденал асоратлар, шикастланишнинг оғирлик кўрсаткичи.

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ЭНДОСКОПИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ГАСТРОДУОДЕНАЛЬНЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ У ТЯЖЕЛОБОЖЕННЫХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Обосновано применение 7 параметров в качестве основных прогностических критериев для оценки состояния пострадавшего с обширной термической травмой, осложненной развитием ожоговой болезни. Комплексный анализ данных критериев даёт возможность создания шкалы прогноза развития острых гастродуоденальных осложнений, высокая достоверность которой позволит прогнозировать развитие указанных осложнений и принимать своевременные профилактические меры

Ключевые слова: ожоговая травма, ожоговая болезнь, гастродуоденальные осложнения, индекс тяжести поражения.

Despite the advancements in modern surgery, burn care, and intensive care, the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of acute gastroduodenal complications (GDC) in burn patients remain not fully understood, which necessitates the search for criteria for selecting an individualized approach for this category of patients [7,8,11]. The most common type of GDC in severely burned patients is hemorrhagic syndrome from the upper gastrointestinal tract [3,9]. The central link in the pathogenesis of erosive and ulcerative lesions of the stomach and duodenum in burn disease is mucosal damage, which is caused by an imbalance of protective mechanisms with increasing endotoxemia and impaired microcirculation in the submucosal layer [5,12].

The development of ischemic lesions, up to wall necrosis, manifests in clinical practice as various motor-evacuation disorders, bleeding from erosive and ulcerative lesions of the stomach and duodenum. All of the above determines the directions of therapeutic tactics in this category of patients, which should include drugs that improve the rheological parameters of blood, stabilize lipid peroxidation processes, and restore tissue respiration indicators [4,6]. According to Bobrovnikov A.E., acute erosions and ulcers of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) are observed in 30.3-66.1% of cases in patients with burn trauma [1,10].

According to Wagner D.O., one of the unfavorable complications of burn disease is gastrointestinal bleeding, which occurs in 10-30% of victims with shock-inducing thermal trauma. Mortality in this category of patients can reach up to 80%, which makes this problem relevant in modern burn care [2,3].

Objective of the study. Predicting the likelihood of developing acute gastroduodenal complications in severely burned patients.

Materials and Methods. The overall study group consisted of 85 patients with extensive burns from 2020-2024, treated in the burn unit of the Samarkand City Medical Association.

Based on data on the course of burn disease (BD) (complicated and uncomplicated) with the development of acute gastroduodenal complications, all patients were divided into two groups: Group 1 consisted of 45 (53%) burn patients in whom burn disease developed with acute gastroduodenal complications within the first 7 days after injury; Group 2 consisted of 40 (47%) patients in whom

BD was not complicated by the development of acute gastroduodenal complications within the first 2 weeks after admission. Patients in Group 1 received H2-histamine receptor blockers.

The results obtained from severely burned patients in both groups were taken into account in the subsequent analysis of the probability of developing acute gastroduodenal complications on the 3rd day from the time of injury, the course during the period of burn shock and burn toxemia, and were processed using methods of variational statistics.

Results and discussion. Given that the patients, prior to the burn injury, did not present with complaints regarding the digestive system and, in some cases, had no pathology in their history upon esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD), the changes that were identified during the endoscopic examination were considered directly related to the thermal factor. Among the patients in the main group, a number of gastroduodenal complications were observed, which were identified during EGD and were grouped into 3 categories: inflammatory lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa, erosive-ulcerative lesions, and motor-evacuation disorders. Moreover, a patient could have a complex of complications within the aforementioned groups, as well as combinations thereof. In the control group patients, the aforementioned complications were not observed, and therefore, we did not perform a comparative analysis between the groups.

Among the inflammatory lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa, it is worth noting such conditions as reflux esophagitis, catarrhal and hemorrhagic gastroduodenitis (Fig. 1).

Among the erosive-ulcerative complications in the injured patients, EGD revealed both superficial (erosive) and deep (ulcerative) lesions, as well as their combinations (Fig. 2).

In addition to inflammatory and erosive-ulcerative complications from the mucosa and submucosal layer, motor-evacuation complications occupied a special place, which aggravated the course of burn disease (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Endoscopic picture of inflammatory lesions of the esophageal and gastric mucosa: A) Reflux esophagitis; B) Catarrhal gastritis; C) Hemorrhagic gastritis.

Fig. 2. Endoscopic picture of erosive-ulcerative lesions of the stomach and duodenum. A) Multiple erosions of the antrum of the stomach, complicated by stopped bleeding. B) Chronic ulcer of the duodenal bulb, complicated by ongoing bleeding; C) Chronic duodenal ulcer, complicated by stopped bleeding.

Fig. 3. Motor-evacuation complications in burn disease: duodeno-gastric bile reflux with gastrostasis.

We studied the dynamics of the endoscopic picture with the presence of the above-mentioned groups of complications in burn disease.

At the same time, despite the ongoing intensive conservative therapy, inflammatory changes persisted for up to 2 weeks from the time of the burn injury. Moreover, while a decrease was characteristic for the inflammatory process in the esophageal mucosa, the opposite trend was observed in relation to the gastric and duodenal mucosa (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Dynamics of inflammatory complications in burn disease (n=45).

Regarding erosive-ulcerative complications, it should be noted that on the 7th day from the time of the thermal injury, 100% of patients had superficial and/or deep lesions of the gastric and duodenal mucosa, which in some cases were complicated by hemorrhagic syndrome (Fig. 5). In the 2nd week, with a favorable course of burn disease, scarring of chronic duodenal ulcers was observed, and therefore, they were excluded as GDC.

Fig. 5. Dynamics of erosive-ulcerative complications in burn disease (n=45).

Motor-evacuation complications responded well to conservative therapy, and when analyzing their dynamics, a significant decrease in both the frequency of their detection and the severity of their expression was noted (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Dynamics of motor-evacuation complications in burn disease (n=45).

Conclusions.

1. Among gastroduodenal complications in burn disease, the most common are inflammatory, erosive-ulcerative lesions and motor-evacuation disorders, and their severity varies depending on the timing of the burn disease and intensive therapy.

2. Catarrhal changes in the mucosa are sensitive to aggression and tend to rapidly penetrate into deeper layers of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) organ. Therefore, timely antisecretory prophylaxis plays an important role in strengthening protective factors.

3. Pathogenetically, the faster the motor-evacuation activity in the gastrointestinal tract is restored, the better the blood circulation in the mucous membranes and the less frequently gastroduodenal complications occur.

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10 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

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